

Recreating an instrument inspired by the glass harmonica using fabrication techniques and physical models.

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the process of recreating a glass harmonica inspired new interface for musical expression. In order to design and implement this interface, a number of technologies have been incorporated in the development process. By combining fabrication techniques like laser cutting and 3D printing, a one octave chromatic scale replica interface has been built. The interaction was facilitated by using a MPR121 capacitive sensing chip paired with an Arduino Uno. The interface controls a physics based model of a glass harmonica. We present a preliminary evaluation of the interface as a solo instrument.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1743, the Irishman Richard Puckeridge had the idea of rubbing the edge of stemmed glasses standing on a table and fill them with water to alter the frequencies of the sounds produced. He called the instrument *seraphim*, or sometimes musical glasses and later glasharfe, orglass harp, glasssharp, glasharp [?]. Different melodies can be played on a set of tuned glasses, when filled with appropriate amounts of water or carefully selected by size, by simply rubbing the edge of the glass with a moist finger. Rubbing rims of glasses in order to produce music became very popular in Europe during the 18th century. Music on glasses has been successfully composed by Mozart, Beethoven, and many others. The instrument invented by Benjamin Franklin was heavily inspired by the work of Richard Puckeridge. Glass harmonicas are musical instruments of two kinds. The first one, invented by Benjamin Franklin, adopts glass bowls turned by a horizontal axle so that one side of the bowl dips into a trough of water. The second one is a combination of wine glasses of different sizes. In its early days there were many variants of the glass harmonica, generally composed of 20 to 54 blown crystal glass or quartz bowls, 37 being a common size (see Figure 1).

In modern times, the glass harmonica has seen some physics based simulations, mainly using digital waveguide models. As an example, in [1] a simulation is presented which uses banded waveguides [2, 3].

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This project is the continuation of a series of experiments whose goal is to recreate some musical instruments from the Danish Musical Instruments' museum using fabrication techniques and sound synthesis. The ultimate goal is to encourage visitors of the museum to play with a replica of the instruments, in order to experience their gestural interaction, playability and sound quality, without touching the precious original counterpart.

Figure 1. Glass harmonica displayed in the National Music Museum - Copenhagen

2. INTERFACE DESIGN

The design process draws inspiration from the original glass harmonica, both in shape and interaction. The historical instrument affords a continuous control of the sound by touching the glass bowls. If the rotation speed or the pressure were not correct, the glass would not resonate. These characteristics have been implemented in the replica instrument with one modification: the rotation speed is optimal by default and the user can alter it by increasing friction on the disks. In order to allow for a more expressive performance, a vibrato feature was designed, and will be described in the following section.

Figure 2. Reproduced glass harmonica

2.1 Physical Interface

The instrument was built using a combination of laser cutting techniques, 3D printing and basic circuitry. It consists of 12 disks, a motor with a built in encoder, a MPR121 capacitive sensing chip, an Arduino Uno, a circuit for regulating the speed, a slip-disk, a pair of buttons, an On/Off switch, a couple of bearings, an aluminum axle, a S3M teeth belt on appropriate sprockets and an enclosure built out of MDF. The disks are fabricated using UP3D Pro printers using ABS filament with a thickness of 0.4 mm and have conductive copper tape on the outside. Their sizes is between 140 mm and 92 mm following a linear decrease of 4mm/disk. Every disk has a 44 * 23 mm core cylinder with a 25 mm square opening to accommodate the axle, 3 support spokes and an outer 20 mm touchable surface (see Figure 3). There is a 2 mm shaft between the touchable surface and the inner opening, through one of the spoke for the wire. The touchable size was inspired by piano key sizes. This shape was chosen in order to obtain a rigid structure, equally balanced, and to keep the 3D printing resources low.

Figure 3. A 3D model of a single disk.

The touchable surface has a rounded profile to allow for an intuitive vibrato. For the same reason the copper tape sits in the center, 0.5 mm lower (see figure 4). All disk were generated using the scripting language in Rhinoceros 3D.

Figure 4. Disk profile - Magnified

The disks sit on a 25 mm square aluminum profile. There are 12 * 23 mm apart 2.5 mm holes in the axle for the connection wire to pass through. The axle ends with M10 threaded caps. On top of allowing the wires to pass through, the axle holds the Adafruit MPR121 board. The capacitive board was placed inside the axle in order to reduce the number of wires needing to pass through the slip ring. The axle sits on two ball bearings. In order to ensure smooth operation, there is a pair of 3d printed spacers for each bearing (figure 5).

Figure 5. Bearing Spacers

At one end of the axle a 40 teeth sprocket is bolted. The sprocket connects to a smaller, 16 teeth one that is attached on the motor axle via a S3M super-high torque timing belt. The ratio 16/40 was selected as a good balance of speed/torque after testing several fitting options. At the other end of the axle a hollow bolt is used to secure it to the bearing, in order to connect slip ring to the MPR121 board. The hollow M10 bolt is non-standard, and was obtained by drilling a 4mm hole using a lathe in a regular bolt. The enclosure is build out of MDF using laser-cutting techniques. It is constructed by having two symmetrical pieces that account for the bottom base and the back, two bearing stands, a motor stand, outer panels and the covers for the electronics. All components are made out of 6mm MDF, except the covers that are 2.5 mm MDF cut in a linear "living hinge" way. This pattern was generated using Inkscape and Living Hinge plugins. Each piece is cut in a way to fit into the adjacent ones, creating a solid, self-sustainable enclosure. Very limited quantity of hot glue has been used to hold it together.

2.2 Electronics

Capacitive sensing is at the core of the interaction, and it was achieved using one Adafruit MPR121 board. This chip senses the capacitance on 12 inputs and is connected to the Arduino microcontroller via the I2C protocol. All the processing necessary to detect touch and contact surface are done in software via an Arduino library provided by the manufacturer. The instrument works in a binary fashion, only accounting for touch/no touch, but it can be extended to detect contact surface without the need for new hardware. The motor used to spin the axle is a 24V/55W tape reel motor powered by a 5V/3A power supply. Its speed is controlled via a TIP120 transistor that receives a PWM signal from the Arduino to its base connector. In order to avoid any current being fed back into the Arduino board, a Zener diode is placed between the motors terminals (see Figure 6) The motor has a high mass rotor that acts like a

flywheel, allowing for smooth rotation speed changes and a pleasant interaction. Another benefit of it can be found in its built in optical encoder that is used to calculate the rotation speed of the axle.

Figure 6. Circuit schematic

In order to obtain a dynamic interaction, the motor has variable speed. The idle speed of the axle (when no disk is touched) is 130RPM with a PWM width of 90%. If the speed decreases under 120 RPM, the PWM width is gradually increased (up to 100%) to compensate for the increased friction from the user. An analog speed reduction behavior is implemented for speed over 130RPM. This system combined with the high mass rotary found in the motor affords for a very dynamic, organic feeling interaction with the instrument. The last electronic components are the two buttons pulled down to ground that are connected to the Arduino's digital pins controlling octaves, a switch before the motor's power line and most importantly a gold covered SRC022D slip ring. The slip ring is a piece of equipment that allows for non-permanent electric connections that are used to bridge the fixed Arduino to the rotating MPR121 board found inside the aluminum axle. The connection between the physical interface and the computer running Max/MSP is an Arduino Uno board. The micro-controller is in charge of touch detection, speed detection, speed regulation and sending data to MaxMSP via serial protocol. There are two external libraries used for this: one for the MPR121 chip [4] and one for generic encoders [5].

3. SOUND SYNTHESIS

The sounds of the glass harmonica were simulated using a friction based model from the Sound Design Toolkit [6] implemented in Max 7. The model consists of an exciter and a resonator. The resonator is implemented using a modal synthesizer where each mode is discretized using the bilinear transform, where three modes tuned at f_0 , $2.4f_0$ and $4.7f_0$ were used. The ratio between the modes was determined by previous recordings made on a wineglass' impulse response [7]. The excitation is implemented using a friction model which simulates the interaction between the finger and the instrument. The friction model is a so-called elasto-plastic friction model, which accounts for the micro

deformation of the frictional interactions [8]. The exciter's model can control both the parameters of the interaction's gesture, such as velocity and force of the frictional contact, as well as parameters which are specific to the adhesion properties between the surfaces in contact.

3.1 Mapping

The interface is connected to Max/MSP where the mapping and sound synthesis is performed. Each disk is mapped to a toggle switch controlling the amplitude of an individual synthesizer. When a touch is detected, the amplitude ascends to 0.8 in 200 ms. The release time is 500 ms and it is triggered when the touch is not detected. These values have been approximated from listening to glass harp samples. It is important to mention that each disk corresponds to an independent instance of a synthesizer algorithm. As mentioned before, the speed is controlling the timbre of the sound, by controlling a global rubbing force in the Max/MSP synth engine simulated by using *sig* object. The usable speed is between 60RPM and 150 RPM and is inversely mapped to values between 0.6 and 0.75, in order to simulate sounds raging from very rough, atonal friction sound to a harmonic almost pure tone. If a speed below 60RPM is detected, the synth engines are turned off to avoid random click/pops and other sounds the algorithm might produce with sub-optimal parameters. Lastly the two octave buttons control the midi starting note for the whole synth. Since the instrument resembles a C octave found on pianos, the starting note is always a multiple of 12, and buttons add or subtract 12 semitones out of the root note.

4. PERFORMING WITH THE INSTRUMENT

In order to gather feedback on the playability of the instrument, we collected qualitative feedback from nine players, 3 females and 6 males with ages between 23 and 47. Out of these persons, 6 of them had musical experience to a certain degree, with one being a professional musician. All performers were requested to explore the instrument and to attempt to play any simple melody. Each of them was exposed to three octaves in random order (C4-B4, C5-B5, C6-B6). The sound was played back through a pair of M-Audio BM5 monitors. Overall, there were no major problems with the instrument and all participants discovered easily how to interact with it. The capacitive sensing system proved to be inconsistent between users. Some disks proved more difficult to trigger or not working at all for certain participants. All but one participants used their fingertips to play, predominantly in a monophonic way. Some explored chords, but this was mostly avoided. All participants understood that each disk represented a different frequency and expected the frequency to increase from left to right or from high to low, so from larger to smaller disks. This was not always the case, since the non-linear friction model sometimes did not start the fundamental frequency of a specific tone but one of its harmonics. This contradicted the users' expectations of a linear evolution in pitch and was reported to limit the exploration. The re-

Figure 7. A novice player experimenting with the glass harmonica

lation between timbre and rotation speed was hardly explored. No participant could understand how to change the timbre, while some reported that they did not expect it to be possible. A few participants explored the possibility of creating new timbres by combining harmonically related notes. Two participants mentioned that some notes cancelled each others, especially in the case of a perfect fifth interval. Only one participant experimented with vibrato. Most users interacted with the instrument in an exploratory way, being more interested in how it worked and how it was controlled. This led to a similar interaction across users: chromatically moving from one note to the other. Only four participants succeeded at playing simple, monophonic melodies. The sound was reported to be suitable for horror movies, sci-fi movies, or Harry Potter universe. Four participants preferred the C6-B6 octave, 4 opted for the C4-B4 one and one appreciated all equally.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we presented a reconstruction of the glass harmonica's instrument originally designed by Benjamin Franklin, as found at the Danish Music Museum. The reconstruction was assessed in laboratory settings by novice performers, who appreciated the quality of the interaction, the look of the instrument and the sound synthesis' quality. The ultimate goal is to exhibit the instrument in the museum, where until now only a Theremin and a reproduction of a piano pedal can be touched, while all the other instru-

ments are enclosed behind a glass wall. Playing with the reconstructed instrument in a museum settings can provide more insight into the validity of reproducing instruments for cultural heritage.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Essl, S. Serafin, P. R. Cook, and J. O. Smith, "Musical applications of banded waveguides," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 51–63, 2004.
- [2] G. Essl and P. R. Cook, "Banded waveguides: Towards physical modeling of bowed bar percussion instruments." in *ICMC*, 1999.
- [3] G. Essl, S. Serafin, P. R. Cook, and J. O. Smith, "Theory of banded waveguides," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 37–50, 2004.
- [4] Adafruit, "Arduino library for the mpr121-based capacitive sensors," https://github.com/adafruit/Adafruit_MPR121, 2017.
- [5] E. Barch, "Arduino libraries - encoder," <https://github.com/ericbarch/arduino-libraries/tree/master/Encoder>, 2013.
- [6] S. D. Monache, P. Polotti, and D. Rocchesso, "A toolkit for explorations in sonic interaction design," in *Proceedings of the 5th Audio Mostly Conference: A Conference on Interaction with Sound*. ACM, 2010, p. 1.
- [7] S. Serafin, P. Huang, S. Ystad, C. Chafe, and J. Smith, "Analysis and synthesis unusual friction-driven musical instruments," 2002.
- [8] F. Avanzini, S. Serafin, and D. Rocchesso, "Interactive simulation of rigid body interaction with friction-induced sound generation," *IEEE transactions on speech and audio processing*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1073–1081, 2005.